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EXPLORING THE EFFECTS OF STUDENT-TEACHER INTERACTION IN INTERDISCIPLINARY EDUCATION FROM ART AND TECHNOLOGY WORKSHOP

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to probe how student-teacher interaction, especially in arts and technology workshops held in Taiwan, influences interdisciplinary collaboration and learning. Using interactive theory, observations made during workshops were analyzed individually to find recurring themes, cross-comparisons between workshops were made, and conclusions based on analysis of data drawn. In order to ensure validity and reliability, triangulation was used to cross-examine collected data. The results show that five factors affect student/instructor interactions: differing backgrounds, language differences, teaching content and purpose of the workshop, requirements of the workshop, and the influence of new relationships.

Keywords: interdisciplinary, arts and technology, student-teacher interaction, workshops

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the vast volume and rapid transmission of information has led to the elimination of many of the boundaries between fields of knowledge. Interdisciplinary collaboration and learning are more popular, especially in the fields of arts and technology. Workshops have become a popular way to spread the knowledge of arts and technology by providing new and timely information. Workshops differ from the regular school system and are a new learning environment, offering different kinds of student-teacher interactions. However, in Taiwan, student-teacher interaction had been less discussed in the fields of interdisciplinary collaboration and learning, with most research papers focusing on

industry collaboration case studies, design teamwork models, or general education research. Therefore, this research emphasizes how student-teacher interaction, especially in workshops, influences interdisciplinary collaboration and the learning process.

The purpose of this research is to probe how student-teacher interaction, especially in arts and technology workshops, influences interdisciplinary collaboration and learning. Three approaches are employed: (1) an exploration of the factors that affect the interactions between students and instructors in workshops; (2) an examination of the role of teaching assistants in workshops; and (3) a clarification of the cross relationships between students, instructors, and teaching assistants.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review covers interaction theory, including group dynamics from both the fields of sociology and psychology; interpersonal and leadership theory, and interdisciplinary collaboration and learning theory. Gorman (1969) found that there are four parts to teacher-student interaction: "initial situation", "activities", "feedback", and "emerging situation". Runkel (1963) presented the information feedback circle and indicated that feedback processes created inter-dependence between teachers and students. Leary (1957) found that there are two dimensions of communication, a Dominance-Submission dimension, and a Cooperation-Opposition dimension. These two dimensions form four teacher-student interaction types, including High influence-High proximity, High influence-Low proximity, Low influence-High proximity, and Low influence-low

proximity. Interpersonal and leadership theory, includes Bavelas’s (1950) five organizational communication patterns and Anderson’s (1984) four communication patterns.

Steinheider and Legrady’s (2004) interdisciplinary collaboration and learning theory is a psychological perspective that found three influences of interdisciplinary collaboration: communication, teamwork, and knowledge sharing. Zhang and Candy (2006) pointed out that the key point is to share domain knowledge, including across different backgrounds and languages. In addition, in arts and technology collaboration, computer technology is also a key point of communication. In the research interdisciplinary education in arts and technology, Legrady (2006) pointed out that interdisciplinary education is full of challenges, but is the way to broaden both teacher and student vision. Fruchter and Emery (1999) found that interdisciplinary learning includes processing from “islands of knowledge”, to “awareness”, “appreciation”, and finally to “understanding”. This learning process could be a basis for evaluating interdisciplinary learning.

METHODOLOGY

This research is a case study of four workshops held in 2009 using qualitative methodology. The four workshops are: “Resonating with nature”, “Post Theater - Express Fight Club”, “Erwin Stache - human-machine interaction”, and “Playaround09 - TechNomads” (see Table 1). Using field research methodology, the researcher attended all four workshops and recorded observations. In addition, unstandardized interviews were conducted with students at random during the workshops and semi-structured interviews were also used to explore the relationships between students and instructors in-depth after each workshop (see Table 2).

Using interactive theory, observations made during the workshops were analyzed individually to find recurring themes, cross-comparisons between workshops were also made, and conclusions based on analysis of the data were then drawn. In order to ensure validity and reliability, triangulation was used to cross-examine collected data, including first hand

field observations and scenarios depicted in detail (see Table 3).

No	Name of Workshop	Duration	Theme
A	Resonating with nature	10-14/8/2009	Technology, Interactive, Design
B	Post Theater - Express Fight Club	30/10-7/11/2009	Technology, Theater, Art
C	Erwin Stache - human-machine interaction	10-17/11/2009	Technology, Interactive, music
D	Playaround09 - TechNomads	7-11/12/2009	Technology, Interactive, music

Table 1. List of Four Workshops.

Table 2. Sources of Analysis Data

Flow	Example
Step 1: Coding the interview data	No. SB-2-10-R4-091103 I felt nervous about the new software and the unfamiliar field of music.
Step 2: Meaning extraction	Between instructors and students there are differing backgrounds which makes for fear of learning.
Step 3: Conclude the theme	Differing backgrounds

Table 3. The flow and example of data analysis process

RESULTS

In order to analyse the interaction between teachers, students, and teaching assistants, each of the four workshops was divided into different phases for observation (see Figure 1). Based on Garman’s (1969) teacher-student interaction and Runkel’s (1963) information feedback circle, the interaction between those phases are depicted diagrammatically (see Figure 2).

The results show that five factors affect student/instructor interactions: differing backgrounds, language differences, teaching content and purpose of the workshop, requirements of the workshop, and the influence of new relationships.

On the basis of these results the following is suggested:

DIFFERING BACKGROUNDS

In interdisciplinary collaboration workshops, students and instructors may come from different backgrounds and hold diverse domain knowledge. Based on the results of interviews, all four workshops had problems caused by differing backgrounds. When it comes to the process of brainstorming, a cognitive gap between students and instructors hindered the interactive process. Students may not understand instructors’ requirements, and at the same time, teachers may provide improper instructions. Both situations limited communication effectiveness. Therefore, instructors should be aware and develop optimum ways of communicating with their students.

Figure 1. Procedure analysis of four workshops

Figure 2. Curriculum content and process induction of four workshops

LANGUAGE DIFFERENCES

The proper transfer of information influences student-teacher interaction. Though there were teaching assistants to do interpretation between students and foreign instructors throughout the workshops, misunderstandings still occurred due to the language divide. Mistakes that occur during discussion can have a huge effect on learning. To bridge the language divide, instructors and students should use images, videos, and body language to improve communication.

TEACHING CONTENT AND PURPOSE OF THE WORKSHOP

Based on these four, workshops can be divided into two approaches based on teaching content. One approach focuses on ideas, and the other on technique. Students who attend the former workshop type will spend more time communicating and developing a concept. Due to limited time and lack of technical background, students need teaching assistants to provide technical support to concentrate their ideas but thereby lose the chance to enhance their technical ability. Alternatively, students can focus on a purely technical approach to

knowledge. Here, although students can improve their technical skills, they do not have the chance to generate deeper concepts within their work.

Teachers can combine these two approaches and make adjustments depending on the purpose of the workshop in order to improve students' learning effectiveness.

REQUIREMENTS OF THE WORKSHOP

Workshop instructors can demand high quality work requiring techniques students may not be familiar with and so put students under great pressure to create work. Workshops with a high technical approach can make the teaching process more autocratic, which may limit students' creativity and cause conflicts between students and instructors. Instructors need to be aware of this pressure and attempt to balance such requirements during the teaching process.

INFLUENCE OF NEW RELATIONSHIPS

The relationships between instructor-student, student-teaching assistant, and student-student are fluid as the core of learning shifts dynamically according to different phases of the curriculum. In the beginning, instructors set up the goal of the

workshop for students to follow. When the curriculum phase comes to the learning of technique, instructors are the center of the learning process. Based on Leary's communication model (1957), teachers have a high-influence on students. When learning shifts to the students' concept phase, students become the center of the process and the impact from their instructors is reduced. These new relationships will influence the conditions and the results of interdisciplinary collaboration and learning accordingly (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Communication Model based on different phases of workshop curriculum content

CONCLUSION

In order to improve the learning effect of interdisciplinary collaboration workshops, especially in the field of arts and technology, well-established interaction between students and instructors is the key point. The results indicate that instructors should be aware of the differing backgrounds and

language gap between themselves and students, and choose their communication methods accordingly. Instructors could use images, videos, and body language instead of oral speaking to achieve communication. In addition, instructors should take note of the purpose of a workshop, with the focus on ideas or techniques changing the role and relationship between instructors and students. Instructors should adjust the proportion of ideas or techniques in their teaching content under different circumstances during a workshop process. In this way, not only student interest in learning but also communication between instructors and students can be enhanced.

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